

Synthesis and Biological Activity of some Pyrido-2-carbox-amido-pyrazoline and-isoxazoline Derivatives

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2-Acetoacetamidopyridine on condensation with aromatic aldehydes yielded the corresponding pyrido-2-carboxamido- α,β -unsaturated ketones which on heating with hydrazine hydrate/phenylhydrazine and hydroxylamine hydrochloride gave the corresponding pyrido-2-carboxamido pyrazoline and isoxazoline derivatives. The biological activity of some representative compounds were tested.

ACETAMIDO derivatives, in general, have been found to possess fungicidal¹, herbicidal² and schistosomicidal activities. Substituted amides in which amido-H has been substituted with heterocyclic moiety³, have been claimed as potential local anaesthetics. A perusal of the above finding reveals that a heterocyclo-carboxamido group may be of significant importance, the presence of which makes a compound biologically active. Again, pyrazoline/isoxazoline derivatives⁴⁻⁷ have also been claimed as potential biologically active compounds. Hence, it was thought that a heterocyclo-carboxamido group, if introduced to pyrazoline/isoxazoline moiety, the resulting compound may have considerable potency. Considering all these factors it was thought worthwhile to synthesise a few pyrido-2-carboxamido pyrazoline/isoxazoline derivatives (Scheme 1) and test their biological action.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Beckmann IR-20 spectrophotometer.

2-Acetoacetamido pyridine⁸ (1): A mixture of 2-aminopyridine (0.01 mol) and ethylacetoacetate (0.01 mol) was heated at 155° for 15 h. On cooling, the colourless crystals of 1 were separated. It was filtered off and then recrystallised from ethanol, (25%), m.p. 112°.

3-(Pyrido-2-carboxamido)-4-aryl-but-3-en-2-one (2): A mixture of 1 (0.01 mol) and an aromatic aldehyde (0.01 mol) was fused for 10 min and the resulting mass was cooled and crystallised from ethanol to yield 2. The results are incorporated in Table 1.

N-Acetyl-3-methyl-4-(pyrido-2-carboxamido)-5-arylpyrazoline (3): A mixture of 2 (0.005 mol), hydrazine hydrate (0.035 mol), ethanol (50 ml) and glacial acetic acid (10 ml) was refluxed for 9 h.

a ; R = *p*-nitrophenyl
 b ; R = *m*-nitrophenyl
 c ; R = 4-methoxy-3-hydroxyphenyl
 Scheme 1 Reagents : (i) R.CHO ; (ii) NH₂.OH.HCl ;
 (iii) Ph.NH₂.NH₂ ; (iv) NH₂.NH₂, H₂O, AcOH.

The resulting solution was concentrated, cooled and poured over ice-water when a yellow product was separated which was filtered off and then crystallised from ethanol to yield 3. The results are incorporated in Table 1.

N-Phenyl-3-methyl-4-(pyrido-2-carboxamido)-5-arylpiprazoline (4): A mixture of 2 (0.005 mol), phenyl hydrazine (0.005 mol), ethanol (50 ml) and piperidine (1 ml) was refluxed for 10 h. The resulting mixture was concentrated, cooled and then poured into acidified ice-cold water when coloured compounds were separated which were filtered off and crystallised from ethanol to yield 4. The results are incorporated in Table 1.

3-Methyl-4-(pyrido-2-carboxamido)-5-aryl-isoxazoline (5): A mixture of 2 (0.005 mol), hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.005 mol), ethanol (50 ml) and KOH (0.005 mol) was refluxed for 12 h. The resulting mixture was concentrated, cooled and poured into ice-water. The yellow compound obtained was filtered off and crystallised from ethanol to yield 5. The results are incorporated in Table 1.

TABLE 1

Compd. no.	R	M p.	Colour	Yield %
2a	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₅	233	White	68
2b	<i>m</i> -NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₅	216	White	61
2c	4-OCH ₃ -3-OH-C ₆ H ₄	142d	White	57
3a	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₅	184	Yellow	62
3b	<i>m</i> -NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₅	178	Yellow	89
3c	4-OCH ₃ -3-OH-C ₆ H ₄	132d	Yellow	59
4a	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₅	157d	Yellow	71
4b	<i>m</i> -NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₅	145	Yellow	52
4c	4-OCH ₃ -3-OH-C ₆ H ₄	195	Yellow	64
5a	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₅	165	Yellow	58
5b	<i>m</i> -NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₅	238	Yellow	72
5c	4-OCH ₃ -3-OH-C ₆ H ₄	260	Yellow	45

Biological screening: Biological screening of some pyrazoline/isoxazoline derivatives was made⁹ and the results are incorporated in Table 2.

TABLE 2—BIOLOGICAL SCREENING DATA*

Compd. no.	<i>B. Subtilis</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>Xanthromonus citrii</i>	<i>B. pumilis</i>
3a	+	-	-	+
3b	-	+	-	-
4a	+	-	-	+
4c	-	+	-	-
5a	-	-	-	+
5b	-	+	-	-
Tetracycline	+++	+++++	+++	+++

*Zone size. + ≡ 6-12 mm, ++ ≡ 12-18 mm, +++ ≡ 18-24 mm, ++++ ≡ 24-30 mm, +++++ ≡ > 30 mm - ≡ No inhibition

Results and Discussion

Pyrido-2-carboxamido- α,β -unsaturated ketones (2), prepared by the condensation of 2-acetoacetamido-pyridine with aromatic aldehydes showed absorption bands at 1700 (conjugated C=O), 1620 (C=C), and 3400 cm⁻¹ (NH). These derivatives of unsaturated ketones (2), when heated with hydrazine hydrate and phenyl hydrazine, the corresponding pyridocarboxamidopyrazolines (3) and (4) respectively were obtained, obviously *via* the initial formation of hydrazone and phenylhydrazone derivatives which cyclised under the experimental conditions. The formation of these pyrazolines was confirmed by their positive Knorr's colour test¹⁰, a characteristic test for arylpyrazolines. The structures of 3 and 4 were fully corroborated by ir spectral results which showed absorption at 1685 (C=O), 1635 (C=N), 1225 (C-N) and 3420 cm⁻¹ (NH). Similarly, 2 on heating with hydroxylamine hydrochloride yielded the corresponding pyrido-2-carboxamido-isoxazoline (5) which showed ir bands at 1660 (C=O), 1605 (C=N) and 3420 cm⁻¹(NH).

The biological activity of some representative compounds was initially tested and it was found that all the compounds exhibit some antibacterial activity against one or the other bacteria but none of the compounds was found to possess any significant biological activity.

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